

Effect of teeth periodontium presence on the bone physiology against stiffer status after implant placement or teeth ankylosis event. Teeth as jaw weakeners: a pivotal concept in the biomechanics

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Abstract

Teeth had special attachment to the alveolar processes of the jaws. These unique anatomical domains considered by anatomists as a specialized joint. It had special molecular signaling. These attachments of the teeth provide unparallel discontinuities in the alveolar processes with long life maintenance due to the nature of the ectomesenchymal tissues and their embryonic origin. The bone mechanical transduction is controlled by osteocytes. Osteocytes need predetermined displacement which is peculiar to each anatomical region. What we had called jaw weakening by the presence of the teeth enable the alveolar process to deform more than unresorbed edentulous alveolar process. This deformation needs to be disclosed in simple model. We had successfully demonstrated this by our current model.

Keywords: Bone, Biomechanics, dental implants, ankylotic teeth, stiffness of bone, jaws weakeners, jaw stiffeners.

1. Introduction

The presence of teeth in the jaws associated with marked effect upon stiffness. (1) This is a macro-mechanical feature. Some authors discuss this issue as damping effect for the dentition's sake. We should discuss the root of this feature rather than the conclusion based upon this feature. The presence of the PD ligament into the context of any biomechanical discussion should be always present. (2)

This macro-feature should be brought to all disciplines. (3) This reduced stiffness had biological arm that maintain the condition and produce the desired effect needed for alveolar process growth. Mechanical activity had passive effect while biological activities had active effects. The biological system had miraculous presentations in all aspects. (4)

This issue had been discussed by many authors, but no one introduce a good representative model from our point of view. We need a model that could be easily interpreted and explained. The conclusion from this simple model will be applied to all the next models and will not stop on the theoretical level but should also affect all of our practical and clinical managements lines. (5)

There are two types of stiffness associated with a presence of teeth

- Passive stiffness effect on the jaws due to the presence of teeth sockets in region other than those with teeth involved directly in the dental function.
- Active stiffness due to the effect of teeth on those enduring direct loading which is directly involved in the transmission of loads due to different dental functions mostly mastication, even phonetics production has a subtle effect upon the teeth. This will be introduced in a separate paper.

The effect of teeth presence will involve effect on a growth as well as in addition to mastication. We had called this effect as anatomical weakening and the sockets as jaw weakeners. In our paper about a proposed mechanical response of the frontal bone due weakening and the resultant effect upon both dynamic and the static performance. (6) Teeth should be always regarded as jaw's weakeners. Any numerical mechanical property or feature of any model response should be hold in mind and recalled in the context of all other next mechanical models that involve jaws, even if this particular feature is not presented. (7) In our current discussion, this feature is teeth periodontal ligaments teeth. The socket effect affects jaws and there is a delicate balance with the presence of weak periodontal ligament response and their dimensions. Toothless socket sometimes regarded by us as a toothed socket with periodontal ligaments. Both had close resemblance to fresh extraction socket from biomechanical point of view. Although they are totally different, but all are far away from post-extraction toothless model without resorption model. (8)

The modern simulation, including medical one, needs many computational resources and simplification is a must. (9) Direct comparison of the two model to the implant model had been done. Model of ankylosis had been supposed to be equal to the model of perfect healing without any resorption in post extraction period. There is huge difference between the ankylosis and the socket that had healing without resorption especially in term of bone orthotropicity and the bony trabecular orientation. Laminated bones structure of the mandible need gigantic super super super computer to represent it and simulate it

Voided bone with presence of teeth sockets and teeth is a feature that need special consideration. Orthotropicity of the bone is another feature they are overlapped on many levels in real model to produce the unique mechanical response of the bone. All of the numerical models are simulating very simple response of the original living bonus response. This model is the first model that should be understood in order to comprehend our remaining models about the growth, orthodontics and trauma. (10) The presence of dental implants passively should be understood under the lights of this model.

As we stated earlier teeth should be regarded as jaws' weakeners or stiffness reducers, while dental implants should be regarded as just jaws stiffeners. Many clinical findings could be understood from implementation of this model. Passive metallic mass is not only associated with dental implants. The usage of heavy metallic hardware in the management of pediatric trauma had significant effect upon the growth by altering the stiffness of the jaws. Accordingly, polymeric osteosynthesis hardware is highly advisable in pediatric age group trauma due to this beneficial feature specifically. The current biomechanical model should be understood well by the surgeons whom choose the heavy schemes of hardware in the management of cases that need reconstruction or repair. Heavy metal dental hardware such as dental implants (e.g. zygomatic implants) will affect trauma response as well as trauma model. (11) This concept should guide all of our management guidelines. (12) I is well known the positional change of the dental implant after cessation of the growth, if they are placed in the stie while the person is in the active growing period.

Finally, we should regard the teeth as bone discontinuities preservers while implants as tetherers. In addition, implant will be associated with overcoritcalization and stress shielding at the same time in different regions. The last 2 phenomena are applied to dental implants or teeth with active loading. While the current model is representing passive effect upon the stiffness. (13)

Methods

In the current study this model had been synthesized utilizing COMSOL Multiphysics® (COMSOL Multiphysics® v. 6.0. www.comsol.com. COMSOL AB, Stockholm, Sweden). We had modified the legend of the postprocessed result to make the models more comprehensible.

Figure 1 These are the dimensions of the used model

In this study, we want to compare the extent by which the bone with well osseointegrated implant is different from dentulous bone in its response when the load is only affecting the bone. We studied a bone model and compared it to:

- Normal tooth, the same tooth model we studied in our other works
- Ankylosed tooth
- Tapered thin titanium implant
- An edentulous bone model which is the benchmark in comparison

We had studied the effect of dentition or implant upon stiffness then trauma response had been studied accordingly in details. We will publish them in the next papers if Almighty God will.

Results and discussion

Always we should remember that this is a representing model which is orthotropic continuous homogenous.

Figure 2 3D model with a transparency to get in depth evaluation

The first evaluation criteria is X field displacement. This estimates the collapse of the socket against the tooth.

Figure 3 this is X field of the displacement of the implant model

The difference in the displacement fields is significantly different. The question is whether a site could affect the remodeling in the remote sites or could remote site sense the change in the surrounding environment mechanically.

Figure 4 this is X field of the displacement of the tooth model

Red region represent positive value and the blue regions represent the negative value

Figure 5 When the bone itself is loaded not the tooth, the bone will collapse making the shape of the socket more elliptical in the case of rounded root shape. This deformation is absent in the case of dental implant

The osteointegration of the bone with the metallic implants in conjunction with the non-compressible nature of the implant itself will deprive the bone from this deformation. Other fields of displacement need to be discerned in order to understand the biomechanical concept of the jaws when titanium implants is introduced inside of the jaws. This must be understood as incremental changes as the teeth are in close proximity to each other.

Next models are of the ankylotic tooth models

Figure 6 Total displacement of the ankylosed tooth model

Figure 7 The displacement is the criteria we had chosen to evaluate stiffness. The red region represents the least displacement. The more figures could assist the researchers to comprehend the whole picture

Figure 8 The displacement is the criteria we had chosen to evaluate stiffness. The red region represents the least displacement

Figure 9 The displacement of the isolated bone model and isolated tooth or implant model should be deeply investigated

Figure 570

Figure 10 Displacement of the isolated ankylosed tooth

Figure 11 Strain energy density of the ankylosed tooth model. The strain energy density had been agreed by the biomechanical community to represent possible remodeling after introduction a change as implant placement

All previous models are representing ankylosed tooth to the bone. The mechanical properties of the engineering materials are close to each other and need to be highly different to demonstrate differences, but the natural living materials are totally different due to many issues such as the orthotropicity.

Next models are of the implant models

Figure 12 Displacement of the implant model

Figure 13 Displacement of the implant model

Figure 14 Displacement of the implant model

Figure 15 Displacement of the implant model, isolated bone sub-model

Figure 16 Displacement of the implant model, isolated implant sub-model

Figure 17 Figure 9 Strain energy density of the implant model. The upper region of the bone analog had more density than the occurred in the model of the tooth. In contrast, the lower part of the model had higher concentration of the density in the tooth model.

The molecular biology is highly affected by the mechanical performance of the skeletal domains. All of the previous models are of the implant model. The implant model is flat threadless tapered design.

Next models are of the tooth models

Figure 18 Displacement of the tooth model. The periodontal ligament component is apparent in the design.

Figure 19 Displacement of the tooth model

Figure 20 Displacement of the tooth model

Figure 21 Displacement of the tooth model for the isolated bone model

Figure 22 Figure 19 Displacement of the tooth model for the isolated tooth sub-model

Figure 23Figure 19 Displacement of the tooth model for the isolated periodontal ligament sub-model.

Figure 24 Figure 9 Strain energy density of the tooth model.

Figure 25 Direct comparison of the tooth model and the implant model in the term of strain energy density. Again, teeth should be always regarded as discontinuity maintainers.

The effect of multiple teeth on the bone will be enormous and incremental.

Next models are of the edentulous non resorption model

Figure 26 This model is the edentulous socket without resorption

Figure 27 Figure 24 This model is the edentulous socket without resorption

Figure 28 Figure 24 This model is the edentulous socket without resorption

Figure 29 Strain energy density of the edentulous model

Figure 30 Direct comparison of the unresorbed edentulous model and the implant model in the term of strain energy density. Again, teeth should be always regarded as discontinuity maintainers.

The edentulous bone had very close displacement to the ankylosed tooth and higher than the titanium implant model. Displacement of the tooth model had the highest value. Strain energy density plot shows a significantly different pattern than the other models. It shows possible bone remodeling patterns in the region away from the force side application with a significant concentrated amount in the preimplant region. This pattern could give a clue about how bone remodeling would affect growth in both the implant and tooth when the growth is still not ceased.

While the bone had plain distribution, the ankylosed and implant model share nearly the same pattern. The study of the bone growth in the case of an ankylosed tooth could provide a picture of the possible pattern of the growth that could result from the placement of an implant in growing children.

Conclusion

The current numerical models shade the light upon the passive effect of the teeth socket on bone performance. This effect is multiplied by the incremental presence of the teeth. Many clinical findings need scientific explanation rather than speculations. Implant placement even if it is out of occlusal load had a significant effect upon the stiffness.

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Mohammed Zahid Saadoon BDS– FKHCMS (Maxillofacial Surgery). During 2014-2024 he was involved in many researches in biomechanics and biomechatronic. He developed many theories in maxillofacial traumatology, craniofacial growth and dental implantology. He developed a unique dental implant system. He has a special interest in mechanical engineering applications in the medical and dental specialties as well as in forensic medicine. He is now working as maxillofacial surgeon in Ashty teaching hospital, largest secondary referral centers in Soran discrete at Kurdistan region / Iraq.